

Accessibility to Poverty Alleviation Programmes for Sustainable Rural Development in South East, Nigeria

Obiageri A. Ogbonna ✉

*Department of Geography and Environmental Management,
University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria*

Andrew. A. Obafemi ✉

*Department of Geography and Environmental Management,
University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria*

Helen Ozeh

11 Salisbury Road, SO40 3HW, Southampton, United Kingdom

Abstract

The study examined accessibility to Poverty Alleviation Programmes (PAPs) and Rural Development in South East Nigeria. The objectives were to identify the various poverty alleviation programmes and their associated basic services, their accessibility levels, and their socio-economic impacts on rural communities sustainable development in the zone. Twenty rural communities were selected using systematic sampling technique and 400 copies of the questionnaire was administered to respondents using random sampling technique. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis, while tables and charts were used for data presentation. Findings showed that 54 major PAPs were identified with their year of establishment ranging from 1959 to 2021 in which majority (88.9%) were Federal Government based while 11.1% were solely from the South East zone of Nigeria. While majority (66.67%) of them were established between 1980 and 1999, findings revealed that 85.19% were still in existence and 14.81% were not. In terms of accessibility to these PAPs, 5.56% were rated excellent, 24.05% good, 38.89% fair while 31.48% were rated poor. Over 60% respondents agreed that the implementation of PAPs has not been effective just as their implementation has not been reaching individuals in the community. The study concludes that although these programmes were established to cater for different sectors ranging from agriculture to unemployed youths or people, very few of the initiatives achieved their goals. It is recommends that individual and governments at all levels should tackle corruption and insecurity in the zone to ensure smooth and successful operation of PAPs.

Keywords: *poverty alleviation programme, rural development, South East Nigeria, rural communities, sustainable development.*

Suggested citation: Ogbonna, O.A., Obafemi, A.A., & Ozeh, H. (2026). Accessibility to Poverty Alleviation Programmes for Sustainable Rural Development in South East, Nigeria. *European Journal of Innovative Studies and Sustainability*, 2(1), 155-168. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2026.2\(1\).10](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2026.2(1).10)

Introduction

Over the years, poverty, globally has remained one of the major issues in policy, development discuss and literature especially on how to tackle it, hence the consideration of poverty reduction as one of the Millennium Development Goals which nations, especially less developed ones, ought to address by

putting in place many poverty reduction strategies (Obamwonyi & Aibieyi, 2014). So, the persistent challenges faced in rural communities over the years, especially in most of the developing countries and Nigeria in particular, has necessitated several multifaceted approach aimed at providing the much needed intervention. One of such measures is what we popularly refer to in Nigeria as Poverty Alleviation Programmes (PAPs), which is usually coordinated by Governments with the support and collaboration of other stakeholders such as the Private sector, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), and the international organizations. (World Bank, 2016, Adamu, 2021 & Chen, 2024).

It is estimated that more than 40% of the world's population lives in poverty, which shows that many people around the globe still struggle to make ends meet. In the same vein, the World Bank (2023) also, estimated that about 700.6 million people is said to live in extreme poverty in September 2023. Several studies reveals that poverty level has decreased in developed countries since the Industrial Revolution. This is attributed to increased production reduced the cost of goods, making them more affordable, just as the advancements in agriculture increased crop yields, as well as food production (Chen, 2024). In the US for instance, the 2022 census, put the number of people in the U.S. who lived in poverty in 2022, to be 11.5% of the nation's population.(Bill, 2023).

In Africa, while a number of countries have been able to lower the poverty rate of their countries, it has not been so for several others. According to a recent report on poverty rate among African countries, Mauritius is ranked as having the lowest poverty rate in Africa, with rates as low as 0.5%, Morocco (2.42%), Algeria (4.5%), Ghana (11.3%) Tunisia (15.1%), and Botswana with around 16.3%. Incidentally, some of these countries also rank among the 10 African countries with the lowest poverty rate, are also adjudged to be among the African countries with the strongest push back against poverty from SDG Index (UNDP, 2023).

On the other side of the divide however, of African countries with the highest share of global population living below the extreme poverty line in 2025, Nigeria rank first along with democratic republic of Congo with 11.7%, followed by Tanzania and Mozambique with 4%. .According to the world Bank report, although, several countries are said to have high poverty rates, Nigeria is however often quoted as having the highest number of people living in extreme poverty based on the World Bank's measure of extreme poverty of people living on less than \$2.15 a day. Other countries with large populations living in poverty include India, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, and Bangladesh. In Nigeria, poverty levels are high and have recently increased, with estimates suggesting that over half the population lives below the poverty line. Specifically, the World Bank reported that the poverty rate rose from 40.1% in 2018 to 56% in 2024, meaning that about 129 million Nigerians are currently living in poverty. This increase is largely attributed to factors like rising inflation and poor economic management (World Bank, 2024).

The nexus between poverty and rural underdevelopment is a complex web of challenges that demands an understanding. There exists a prevalent opinion that rural communities are often bereft with limited access to education, healthcare, and markets, as well as infrastructural deficiencies leading to the exacerbating cycle of poverty, which has in-turn attracted several poverty alleviation programs intended to fastrack rural development initiatives. In any event, the success of these interventions is often premised on their ability to address the specific challenges and meet the need of these rural communities in a sustainable and inclusive way. This is why governments all of the world often put social welfare and other poverty alleviation programs in place to help lift individuals, families, and communities out of poverty.

As a result of these underdevelopment and poverty in the land, the country ha continue to witness such anti-social activities and vices like armed robbery, cultism, drug trafficking, prostitution, child labour and trafficking, ritual killings, political thuggery and assassinations, etc. (Olabisi, et al 2020, and Obamwonyi & Aibieyi, 2014; Orji, 2005). This phenomenon has left the country highly underdeveloped socially, economically and technologically. This has created a situation of mass graduate unemployment and other social vices articulated from the foregoing. Highly skilled trained manpower and infrastructure facilities are either under-utilised or non-existent (Orji, 2005). The various government programmes aimed at

eradicating or alleviating poverty have not stood the test of time, as they have not actually impacted positively on the people (Orji, 2005).

Among such National Poverty Alleviation Programme (NAPEP) include the National Accelerated Food Production Project (NAFPP), Green Revolution, Agricultural Development Programme (ADP), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), People's Bank and so on. The inability of these various poverty alleviation initiatives put in place to alleviate or eradicate poverty in the country or achieved the goals of their establishment have witnessed several criticisms. (Oshewolo, 2010, World Bank, 2016, Adamu, 2021) ,Rather than the poverty situation to improve, Nigeria has now assumed a status of being derogatorily described as the poverty capital of the world.

Recently, there has been a reorientation of the government's focus towards developing Community-Based Poverty Reduction using Community Driven Development approach (World Bank, 2021; Akinlade, Adeyonu, & Carim-Sanni, 2015). In Nigeria, under this approach, several programmes have been implemented and some are still on. Local Empowerment and Environmental Management Programme (LEEMP); Community-Based Poverty Reduction Project (CPRP) and Community and Social Development Project (CSDP) are social Community Driven Development (CDD) projects while National Fadama Development Project (*Fadama II and III*) is economic CDD project (World Bank, 2022; Akinlade, Adeyonu, & Carim-Sanni, 2015). However, these numerous poverty alleviation programmes initiated by successive governments in Nigeria, poverty remains pervasive, especially in rural areas of the South East geopolitical zone.

In spite of the several initiatives put in place to mitigate or reduce the high level of poverty rate, reduction of youth unemployment and upgrading of several critical rural infrastructure aimed at fostering rural development, there remain the huge challenge of accessibility. (NBS, 2022; Work Bank, 2024). There are also issues relating to the sustainability of the various poverty alleviation programmes put in place by the various state governments as well as other non-governmental interventions aimed at improving living standards, enhancing income generation, and promoting sustainable rural development in the region. (Odejide, 1997; NEEDS, 2004; Adamu, 2021). Although, there is a consensus among scholars that poverty, which is often determined by socioeconomic status, ethnicity, gender, and geography is a difficult cycle to break and can pass from one generation to the next. Yet, government at different levels must ensure that its people are helped out of poverty, hence the different initiatives put in place to address poverty.

It is to this end that this study investigates accessibility to poverty alleviation programmes and their impact on sustainable rural development in the South East zone of Nigeria. The study specifically identified the various poverty alleviation programmes and their related basic services in the zone, their accessibility levels, and the socio-economic impact of these interventions on rural communities sustainable development.

Conceptual and Empirical Review

Concept of Poverty and Rural Development

According to the World Bank (1999), poverty is hunger; lack of shelter; being sick and being unable to go to school; not knowing how to read; not being able to speak properly; not having a job; fear for the future; losing a child to illness brought about by unclean water; powerlessness, lack of representation and freedom (Adekoya, 2014). Poverty is the economic condition in which people lack sufficient income to obtain certain minimal levels of health services, food, housing, clothing and education which are necessities for standard of living (World Bank, 2011; Manufacturers Association of Nigeria, 2003). Furthermore, Obamwonyi & Aibieyi (2014). described poverty as having a material dimension, physical dimension, and psychological dimension. To them, material dimension has to do with economic issues like income and asset, the physical dimension has to do with both physiological and social dimensions

like hunger, poor health, and poor education, whereas, the psychological dimension relates to both sociological and political; which includes voice, freedom, and power (Manufacturers Association of Nigeria, 2003).

To Olabisi et al (2020), the various definitions and measures of poverty lead to two perspectives which are income poverty and lack of basic need poverty. To Chen(2024), the term poverty refers to the state or condition in which people or communities lack the financial resources and other essentials for a minimum standard of living, hence they are unable to meet their basic human needs. It is to this effect that poverty is a socioeconomic condition that is the result of multiple factors—not just income. These factors include race, sexual identity, sexual orientation, and access to education, among others. Poverty is also regarded as inability within ability to meet the basic necessities of life like food, shelter, and clothing. In other words, people are considered poor when their measured standard of living in terms of consumption is below the poverty line, that is, the value of income or consumption necessary to attain the minimum standards of nutrition and other necessities of life (Ravilion & Bidani, 1994, & Ravillion, 2016; Manufacturers Association of Nigeria, 2003).

From the foregoing therefore, the concept of poverty can be summarized as a phenomenon that exists at national, community, household and individual levels; and as a variable to measure development. At the national level, poverty represents a state of general socio-economic underdevelopment arising from poor human resource endowment, poor natural resources endowment, low productivity and stagnating national income or gross domestic product, inadequate availability of social and infrastructure facilities and services and a general inability to provide a minimally decent level of living for the ordinary citizens. At the community level, poverty is a state of general socio-economic deprivation arising from environmental and natural resources degradation, inadequate access to social services and basic infrastructure, inadequate local employment and income generating opportunities and general appearance of physical decay and wasting of community assets (Orji, 2005; Manufacturers Association of Nigeria, 2003).

Development on the other side has remained a concept with universal currency, appeals and usage, but yet with a consensus on what development precisely means both conceptually and operationally. Nevertheless, there is a general consensus that development connotes among others, the progress, improvement, upliftment or desirable changes in the totality of certain aspect of human life. This could be social, economic, political or technological change. In classical philosophical school, it could be referred to as the good life, which in relative terms, varies from one person to another (Orji, 2005). Rural development therefore involves efforts that are economic and social in nature intended to encourage concepts of retention, growth, and expansion in areas outside cities, including improving quality of life for rural residents through such activity (Sharma, 2022; Atkinson, 2017). According to Atkinson (2017), rural development is not a straightforward matter, nor an easily addressed question, as the nature of rural areas has shifted, from primarily a farming perspective to one that encompasses a range of possibilities. For the reason of this shift in context and perspectives, rural development may thematically focus on bottom-up views and consider social change and the needs of the neglected, to create a safety net that considers issues beyond jobs or increased wealth (Landini et al. 2014) and shares in common with sustainable development (Khongsatjaviwat & Routray 2015; Atkinson, 2017).

Given the understanding that any poverty alleviation programs should address rural development, the World Bank therefore viewed rural development as a strategy designed to improve the economic and social life of a specific group of people; the rural poor. It involves extending the benefits of development to the poorest among those who seek a livelihood in the rural areas. (World bank, 2022).

In the same vein, Atkinson (2017) opined that in any rural development program, there is a need to ensure that such programs are meeting their intent, including both the short-run and long-term development in a particular area. For instance, some of the successful rural development plans according to Buragohain and Landge (2014), are those with outcomes that benefit communities more generally (i.e.,

that aid several potential projects, through infrastructure improvements, or help the marketability of a place) can be explained through qualitative approaches, relying upon methods like focus groups, rather than quantitative means that would be more appropriate in urban settings. Simply put therefore, rural development refers to the planned efforts undertaken to eliminate poverty, enhance resilience, promote ecological sustainability and build capacity to meet these challenges faced by the rural areas (Sharma, 2022).

Empirical Review

Poverty became widespread after the implementation of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in Nigeria. Olayemi (2017) highlighted that over-reliance on oil revenue has undermined agricultural and industrial sectors, leading to limited employment opportunities and widespread economic vulnerability. The rapid rise in poverty in Nigeria may allegedly be attributed to political unrest caused by successive military takeovers. Corruption and poor governance are also widely acknowledged as root causes. According to Okonjo-Iweala and Osafo-Kwaako (2007), misappropriation of public funds and weak institutional frameworks hinder economic development and equitable wealth distribution. The failure to implement effective poverty alleviation policies is attributed to political instability and policy inconsistency (Ogunyemi, 2019). Also, Obadan (2002) emphasizes that limited access to quality education restricts social mobility and job prospects for the poor. Similarly, inadequate infrastructure and limited social safety nets disproportionately affect marginalized communities.

Among the several studies on poverty and poverty alleviation in Nigeria is that one by Danaan (2018), who explores the theoretical nature of poverty in Nigeria. He argued that poverty is complex and multidimensional because it is influenced by cross-cutting factors that affects the social, psychological, economic and cultural spheres of existence. While the study suggests improved knowledge and strategies on the causal factors of poverty, it argues that empowering people to develop resilience to manage and overcome it within the range of their resources and capabilities should be deployed for reducing poverty (Abubakar, et al 2022; Omaku, Musa, & Ikwuyatum, 2022).

On the impact of government poverty alleviation programmes in Nigeria, much have been said that these programmes have not significantly impacted the people. For the south east zone for instance, Okonkwo (2015), suggests in his study that sustainable poverty reduction strategy should not focus narrowly on social welfare measures, rather assets redistribution and creation of incentive structures that can enhance the rate and pattern of economic growth should be seen as essential component (Omaku, Musa, & Ikwuyatum, 2022). Similaly, Omemma and Okafor (2014) evaluated the implementation of national poverty reduction programme in Enugu State of Nigeria. Using cross-sectional and exploratory methods of data collection and analysis, the study discovered that, compared to most states in other parts of the country, Enugu State has a low poverty profile owing to the relative positive impact of the implementation of poverty alleviation programme (Omaku, Musa, & Ikwuyatum, 2022).

On the overall purpose of most of the poverty alleviation strategies adopted in Nigeria, they were well focused on rural areas and agricultural sector. It was observed that most of these programmes before and during Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) were supply driven which could not meet the needs of the poor and so they had little effect in alleviating poverty. The poverty alleviation measures implemented so far have focused more on growth, basic needs and rural development approaches (Omaku, Musa, & Ikwuyatum, 2022).

By the year 2000, Nigeria's population was put at about 120 million, and the country was said to be liberally endowed with about 98 million hectares of cultivable land. Its mineral resources included petroleum, tin, columbite, iron ore, lead, zinc found in abundance across the country. It was this period that the federal government of Nigeria launched another poverty alleviation scheme called the National Poverty Empowerment programme (NAPEP). The scheme was given a takeoff grant of N6 billion (\$42.8m) in January 2001, which was for establishing NAPEP structures in 36 states, the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja and 774 local government councils. Part of the money was also used in the NAPEP

employment generation intervention through the training of unemployed youths and graduates in various sectors, as well the purchase and delivery of the KEKE-NAPEP a three-wheeler vehicle project involving 2000 units in all the state capitals of Nigeria. Others include the establishment of 147 youth information centers across the senatorial districts, the delivery of informal micro credit ranging from N10,000 (\$71) to N50,000 to 10,000 beneficiaries most of whom were women with such a massive fund at its disposal, but the question remains how did NAPEP fare in its attempt at poverty alleviation (Akewushola, Olateju, & Adeyemi, 2007).

Materials and Methods

The study location (Figure 1.1) comprises five states namely Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo states. The area lies between latitudes $4^{\circ} 45' 40''$ and $7^{\circ} 49' 12''$ north of the equator and between longitudes $5^{\circ} 59' 00''$ and $9^{\circ} 56' 00''$ East of Greenwich. It is bordered in the South by the Atlantic Ocean. Delta State lies to the West, the north Savanna States of Benue and Kogi to the North, and the sub-equatorial Cameroon Republic to the East (Onuegbu, Obafemi, & Eludoyin, 2021). South Eastern Nigeria possesses varying physical features and hence varying geographical conditions. It has an area of 75,488 square kilometers.

Figure 1. South-Eastern Nigeria Showing the States

Source: OSGOF, 2024

The data used in this study covers a sample of 2 Local Government Areas (LGAs) in each of the five states in the South Eastern Nigeria and 2 communities which were randomly chosen from the selected LGAs for the data collection. 400 copies of modified Likert scale format questionnaire were used to elicit information and data from the respondents from the rural communities. The study employed both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyze the data obtained from the survey. Descriptive statistics involved the use of percentages and frequency was used to amplify the importance of some of the findings. Inferential statistics such as the Spearman's rank correlation statistics were used to test the hypotheses considered more appropriate for questionnaires or qualitative data that does not come from

probability density function since it is a non-parametric method. According to Iheaka (2023), for example, the null hypothesis which states that the error terms are homoscedastic is to be rejected if and only if the calculated SRC test statistic, γ_i , is greater than or equal to the critical value (that is, H_0 is to be rejected iff $\gamma_i \geq 0.5$).

The test statistic for the Spearman Rank Correlation Test is given by

$$\gamma_i = 1 - 6 \left[\frac{\sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)} \right] \quad (1)$$

where n is the number of observations and d_i is the difference between the ranks and the corresponding each pair, $(|e_i|, x_i)$ given by

$$d_i = R_{|e_i|} - R_{x_i} \quad (2)$$

where R_{x_i} is the rank of the individuals X -variables and $R_{|e_i|}$ is the rank of absolute value of the error terms, e_i .

The critical value for this Spearman's Rank correlation test is given as 0.5, this implies that a high rank correlation coefficient exists when γ_i is greater than or equal to 0.5 (that is, $\gamma_i \geq 0.5$) (see, for example, Nwankwo, 2011).

Results and Discussion

The result obtained from the survey shows that the summary of the existence of poverty alleviation programmes and their existence level. It is revealed that 85.19% were still in existence while 14.81% were not in existence. This shows that majority of the poverty alleviation programmes were still in existence. However, the summary of the sector faced by the poverty alleviation programme displayed in Figure 4.4 showed that agriculture only attracted the attention of majority of the poverty alleviation programmes which was 16 (29.63%) of the total number of the programmes in the South Eastern Nigeria. This is followed by the alleviations programmes which addressed more than one major sectors and this covered 27.78% and 9.26% by those poverty alleviation programmes addressing education. Thus, employment had 5.56%, housing had 1.85%, empowering people had 1.85% and infrastructural development also had 1.85%. (Table 1).

Table 1. Summary of the Sector the Poverty Alleviation Faced and Achieved

Sector Focus	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Agriculture Only	16	29.63
Trading Only	1	1.85
Agriculture and Trading	4	7.41
Housing	1	1.85
Education	5	9.26
Electricity	1	1.85

Employment	3	5.56
Employment/Agriculture	2	3.70
Empowering People	1	1.85
Health	3	5.56
Land construction/ development	1	1.85
Multi sector	15	27.78
Infrastructural Development	1	1.85
Total	54	100.00

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2025

Table 2 presents the summary of accessibility to poverty alleviation programmes in South East Nigeria. Findings shows responses of the PAPs rating with only 5.56% having excellently rating, 24.05% were rated good, 38.89% were rated fair while 31.48% were rated poor. This shows that majority (70.37%) of the poverty alleviation programmes did not really achieve their objectives and people had low or no accessibility and their rate of accessibility was not encouraging. This would have affected so many inhabitants of this region because the expectation of being alleviated from their lives of penury has not been achieved; despite the fact of many of the living dead poverty alleviation programmes.

Table 2. Summary of Accessibility of Poverty Alleviation Programmes in South East

Rate of Accessibility	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Excellent	3	5.56
Good	13	24.07
Fair	21	38.89
Poor	17	31.48
Total	54	100.00

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2025

The graphical representations using bar charts which include Categories of Respondents Benefiting from the Poverty Alleviation Programme and Income after the Poverty Alleviation Programmes are shown in Figure 2 (a-d).

Figure 2a. Age of the Respondents

Figure 2b. Marital Status of the Respondents

Figure 2c. Occupational Status of the Respondents

Figure 2d. Educational Status of the Respondents

In Table 3, the correlations between socio-economic characteristics and employment and the analysis reveals that age, annual income, marital status, occupation status, education status, religion, gender and household size correlated significantly and positively with employment as the correlation coefficients (r) was 0.921, 0.916, 0.940, 0.863, 0.892, 0.940, 0.861, and 0.875 respectively.

Table 3. Levels of Socio-Economic Impacts on Income Generation, Employment and Access to Basic Services

	Very Low	Low	Moderate	High	Very High	Total
Socio-economic Impacts on income generation						
Age	29	50	89	109	118	395
Annual Income	56	84	57	113	85	395
Percentage (%)	14.18	21.27	14.43	28.61	21.52	100.00
Marital Status	26	53	82	125	109	395
Percentage (%)	6.58	13.42	20.76	31.65	27.59	100.00
Occupational Status	49	50	147	74	75	395
Percentage (%)	12.41	12.66	37.22	18.73	18.99	100.00
Educational Status	102	14	61	156	62	395
Percentage (%)	25.82	3.54	15.44	39.49	15.70	100.00
Socio-economic Impacts on employment						
Age	14	65	81	118	117	395
Percentage (%)	3.54	16.46	20.51	29.87	29.62	100.00
Annual Income	41	95	52	124	83	395
Percentage (%)	10.38	24.05	13.16	31.39	21.01	100.00
Marital Status	39	57	79	115	105	395
Percentage (%)	9.87	14.43	20.00	29.11	26.58	100.00
Occupational Status	58	52	75	174	36	395
Percentage (%)	14.68	13.16	18.99	44.05	9.11	100.00
Educational Status	15	57	85	109	129	395
Socio-economic Impacts on access to basic services						
Age	26	74	56	102	137	395
Percentage (%)	6.58	18.73	14.18	25.82	34.68	100.00

Annual Income	62	78	69	114	72	395
Percentage (%)	15.70	19.75	17.47	28.86	18.23	100.00
Marital Status	45	51	73	109	117	395
Percentage (%)	11.39	12.91	18.48	27.59	29.62	100.00
Occupational Status	63	50	81	55	146	395
Percentage (%)	15.95	12.66	20.51	13.92	36.96	100.00
Educational Status	19	53	70	113	140	395
Percentage (%)	4.81	13.42	17.72	28.61	35.44	100.00

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2025

Table 3 showcase the poverty alleviation programmes and the rate of accessibility and implementation of each of the initiatives in the South Eastern Nigeria. Against each of the initiatives, the rate of accessibility and implementation ranged from poor to excellent. For the poor among them included rural banking program, The Better Life Programme, Low Cost Housing Scheme, People's Bank of Nigeria, The Small Scale Enterprises Scheme (SSES), The Vocational Skill Development, Conditional Grant Scheme for Millenium Development Goals, You Win, #500bn Social Welfare Programmes, Nigerian Agricultural Insurance Corporation (NAIC), The Rural Employment promotion (REP) from NDE, The National Directorate of Employment (NDE), The Special Public Works (SPW), Operation Feed the Nation (OFN), and Green Revolution (GR).

The alleviation programmes that had fair ratings regarding the accessibility and implementation of poverty alleviation included Farmers Development Union, Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP), Anambra State Cooperative Development Agency, Abia State Cooperative Federation, Family Support Programme (FSP), The Directorate of Foods, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), National Poverty Eradication Programme (NAPEP), Roll Back Malaria, HIV/AIDS Initiative, The Subsidy Reinvestment and Empowerment Program known as 'SURE-P', The Youth Entrepreneurship Support (YES) Programme, Micro Credit Scheme, Poverty Alleviation Programme (PAP) and Presidential Initiatives on Rice, Cassava, Vegetable Oil, and Tree Crop Development Programmes. The poverty initiative programme that are rated good included Imo Self-Help Organisation (ISHO), National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA), Women Farmers Association of Nigeria (WOFAN), Community Banks, Women Cooperative Societies, NEPA District Co-operative Thrift and Loan Saving Association, Enugu, National Commission for Mass Literacy; and Women and Youth Employment Scheme (W-YES). The excellently rated poverty alleviated programme included Guinea Worm Eradication Program, Lift Above Poverty Organization (LAPO) and Universal Basic Education (UBE).

Figure 3. Summary of the Sector the Poverty Alleviation Faced and Achieved

Table 4 displays the crosstabulation of the rates of accessibility to the poverty alleviation programme and period. Before 1970, the alleviation programme was rated good and it was 100%. So, between 1970 and 1979 were 33.33% each for the rates of good, fair and poor respectively. It was shown that the alleviation programme between 1980 and 1989 with excellent rating was 7.1% and that of good was 7.1% while 64.3% was meant for the poor rating. Infact, the highest poor rating was experienced among the alleviation programmes established during this era. Between 1990 and 1999, 13.3% were excellent and was found to produce the highest among the periods while 46.7% of the alleviation programme of the fair rating. Between 2000 and 2009, majority (75%) of the total poverty alleviation programme during this period had fair rating. Between 2010 and 2019, the number of poverty alleviation programmes for good, fair and poor ratings had 33.3% each. The only one poverty alleviation programme established after 2019 was rated poor. Thus, the goals of the existing alleviation programmes that have fair or poor rates concerning accessibility especially those between 1980 and 1989, and between 2000 and 2009 should be attended to for greater achievement.

Table 4 Crosstabulation of the Rate of Accessibility to Poverty Allev. Programmes in South Eastern Nigeria

Period	Rates								Total Freque ncy	Total Percenta ge (%)
	Excellent		Good		Fair		Poor			
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Before 1970	0	0.0	1	100.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	1.85
1970-1979	0	0.0	3	33.3	3	33.3	3	33.3	9	16.67
1980-1989	1	7.1	1	7.1	3	21.4	9	64.3	14	25.93
1990-1999	2	13.3	5	33.3	7	46.7	1	6.7	15	27.78
2000-2009	0	0.0	1	12.5	6	75.0	1	12.5	8	14.81
2010-2019	0	0.0	2	33.3	2	33.3	2	33.3	6	11.11
After 2019	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100.0	1	1.85
Total	3	0.0	13		21	0.0	17		54	100.00
Percent. (%)	5.56		24.07		38.89		31.48		100.0	

In Table 5, the correlations between socio-economic characteristics and access to basic services and the analysis reveals that age, annual income, marital status, occupation status, education status, religion, gender and household size correlated significantly and positively with access to basic services as the correlation coefficients (r) was 0.484, 0.686, 0.924, 0.567, 0.858, 0.796, 0.681, and 0.557 respectively.

Table 5. Correlations between Socio-Economic Characteristics and Access to Basic Services

	Access to basic services	Age	Annual	Marital Status	Occupational Status	Educational Status
Access to basic services	1					
Age	.484*	1				
Annual income	.686*	.711*	1			
Marital Status	.924*	.552*	.675*	1		
Occupational Status	.567*	.818*	.807*	.595*	1	
Educational Status	.858*	.346*	.466*	.880*	.428*	1

Note: *. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Researcher's Analysis, 2025.

Discussion

Findings showed that 54 major poverty alleviation programmes were identified with their year of establishment ranged from 1959 to 2021 in the South Eastern Nigeria. The major focus included farming, trading or small business, youth employment especially in the rural areas. Majority (88.9%) of the poverty

alleviation were Federal Government based while 11.1% were solely from the South Eastern Region of Nigeria. Findings showed that 18.52% of the poverty alleviation programmes were found between 1970 and 1979, 24.07% were between 1980 and 1989, 27.78% were found between 1990 and 1999, 14.81% were found between 2000 and 2009 while 11.11% were found between 2010 and 2019.

Findings showed that the rate of accessibility and implementation of each of the initiatives in the South Eastern Nigeria is low. Against each of the initiatives, the rate of accessibility and implementation ranged from poor to excellent, as earlier posited by Okonjo-Iweala and Osafo-Kwaako (2007) and Omemma & Okafor (2014). The excellently rated poverty alleviated programme included Guinea Worm Eradication Program, Lift Above Poverty Organization (LAPO) and Universal Basic Education (UBE) which are just 5.56% of the total number of the poverty alleviation programmes identified. Findings showed that 85.19% were still in existence while 14.81% were not in existence. This shows that majority of the poverty alleviation programmes were still in existence. Agriculture only attracted the attention of majority of the poverty alleviation programmes which was 16 (29.63%) of the total number of the programmes in the South Eastern Nigeria. Findings showed that majority (70.37%) of the poverty alleviation programmes did not really achieve their objectives and people had low or no accessibility and their rate of implementation was not encouraging. The performance ratings of poverty alleviation programmes in the South Eastern region of Nigeria revealed that 12.41% perceived excellent, 20.25% perceived good, 27.34% perceived fair, while 40% perceived poor of the total number of respondents. Study showed that majority (75.19%) have not benefited from the poverty initiatives in the South Eastern Nigeria. The main occupation with the highest beneficiary of the poverty alleviation intervention in the South Eastern Region was farmers (38.99%).

Majority (77.47%) of the respondents that are of minimum of 30 years would have some experience and more robust information concerning the issue of poverty alleviation programmes in the South Eastern Region of Nigeria. More than 70% were singles and married in the study area. However, 70.89% of total respondents had between 1 and 5 persons in their household. More than 60% of the population were not gainfully employed and this shows that they required assistance which could be informed by different initiative in which poverty alleviation programme is included. Over 90% were educated and that shows that majority can read and write. It is found that 24.56% agreed to having accessibility to credit facilities while 75.44% had no access. This shows that majority are not really having access to credit facilities in the study area and majority relied upon cooperative societies, commercial banks, community bank and merchant bank, thus agreeing with the findings of Abubakar, et al (2022).

Findings showed that majority of total respondents agreed that the implementation of poverty alleviation programme has not been done effectively; benefits of the programme have not been felt in the community and residents, thus aligning with Olabisi, et al (2020). The handlers of the programmes have not been making frantic effort to do follow up on the success of the programme; the implementation of the programme has not been reaching individuals in the community, agreeing with Okonkwo (2014) and Ogunyemi 2019), the community has not been witnessing a rapid development as a result of the poverty alleviation programme and the community cannot boast of having enough food and adequate health care facilities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The accessibility of individuals to the poverty alleviation programmes and implementation has been so poor that many of the programmes found it difficult to be successful. Also, some cultural and environmental issues were found to have continued to trigger poverty in the South Eastern Nigeria. The study reveals that, in as much it is true that Nigeria is not in want of public policies, given the avalanche of policies put in place by the government on several critical issues that ought to foster social, economic and physical development across the rural and urban landscape of Nigeria, their implementation and accessibility to them remains of great concern.

The study concludes that there are many poverty alleviation programmes established to cater for different sectors ranging from agriculture to unemployed youths or people, but very few of the initiative achieved their goals. The major problems making it difficult to achieve the goal of the poverty alleviation programmes in the South East included corruption and insecurity. The accessibility of individuals to these programmes and their implementation has been so poor that many of the programmes found it difficult to be successful. A larger proportion of the population especially in the rural communities have limited access to the these poverty alleviation programs, hence there life were not transformed by them.

The study recommends that there should be adequate accessibility of poverty alleviation programmes to ensure the achievements of its goals. It calls for a recalibration in the implementation approaches where Government at all levels and all stakeholders should strategise with renewed strength and commitment to reduce or totally eradicate the plague of poverty in the South Eastern Nigeria. This implies that the development and empowerment through PAPs requires increased funds and grants for it to achieve its lofty goals of lifting people out of multi-dimensional poverty confronting Nigerian limiting social and economic development of the nation.

References

- Adekoya, A. O. (2014). Analysis of farm households poverty status in Ogun States, Nigeria. *Asian Economic and Financial Review*, 4(3), 325–340.
- Akewushola, R. O., Olateju, O. I., & Adeyemi, O. T. (2007). Poverty, unemployment and growth in Nigeria: The role of entrepreneurship. *Lex et Scientia International Journal*, 14, 157–166.
- Akinlade, R. J., Adeyonu, A. G., & Carim-Sanni, A. (2015). Income inequality and poverty among farming households in Southwest, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development*, 7(1), 59–67.
- Amin, S. (1976). *Unequal development: An essay on the social formations of peripheral capitalism*. Monthly Review Press.
- Atkinson, C. L. (2017). Rural development. In A. Farazmand (Ed.), *Global encyclopedia of public administration, public policy, and governance* (pp. 1–7). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-31816-5_1014-1
- Cleaver, F. (1999). Paradoxes of participation: Questioning participatory approaches to development. *Journal of International Development*, 11(4), 597–612. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1099-1328\(199906\)11:4%3C597::AID-JID594%3E3.0.CO;2-Q](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1099-1328(199906)11:4%3C597::AID-JID594%3E3.0.CO;2-Q)
- Gordon, D., & Spicker, P. (1998). *The international glossary on poverty*. Zed Books.
- Hoebink, P. (2000). Development co-operation and poverty alleviation. In W. Pansters, G. Dijkstra, P. Hoebink, & E. Snel (Eds.), *Rethinking poverty: Comparative perspective from below*. Van Gorcum.
- Iheaka, V. C. (2023). *On identifying and correcting heteroscedasticity in linear regression modelling* (Master's thesis). Imo State University.
- Khwaja, A. I. (2001). *Can good projects succeed in bad communities? Collective action in the Himalayas* (Faculty Research Working Paper RWP01-043). Harvard Kennedy School.
- Kleemeier, E. (2000). The impact of participation on sustainability: An analysis of the Malawi rural piped scheme program. *World Development*, 28(5), 929–944. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X\(99\)00154-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0305-750X(99)00154-3)
- Mansuri, G., & Rao, V. (2004). Community-based and -driven development: A critical review. *World Bank Research Observer*, 19(1), 1–39. <https://doi.org/10.1093/wbro/lkh012>

- Manufacturers Association of Nigeria. (2003). *Nigeria business directory: Under the auspices of the Commonwealth Heads of Government Meeting*. Author.
- McGee, R. (1998). Commentary: Poverty, livelihoods, and policy in Uganda and Kenya. *IDS Bulletin*, 29(4), 105–115. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1759-5436.1998.mp29004013.x>
- Mosse, D. (1997). The symbolic making of a common property resource: History, ecology and locality in a tank-irrigated landscape in South India. *Development and Change*, 28(3), 467–504. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-7660.00051>
- Obadan, M. I. (2002). Poverty reduction in Nigeria: The way forward. *CBN Economic and Financial Review*, 39(4), 159–188.
- Ogunyemi, B. (2019). Governance and poverty reduction in Nigeria: A critical appraisal of policy interventions. *African Journal of Governance and Development*, 8(2), 92–107.
- Okonjo-Iweala, N., & Osafo-Kwaako, P. (2007). *Nigeria's economic reforms: Progress and challenges*. Brookings Institution.
- Olayemi, S. O. (2017). A survey of poverty in Nigeria: Causes, effects and solutions. *Journal of Economic Development Studies*, 5(1), 15–24.
- Omake, A. A., Musa, M., & Ikwuyatum, B. A. (2022). An assessment of poverty reduction programmes in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management Research*, 8(3), 69–76. <https://doi.org/10.56201/ijssmr.v8.no3.2022.pg69.76>
- Onimode, B., & Synge, R. (1995). *Issues in African development*. Heinemann Educational Books.
- Onuegbu, W., Obafemi, A. A., & Eludoyin, O. S. (2021). Hazard perception and awareness level of traders in selected market centres in South-Eastern Nigeria. *Global Scientific Journal*, 9(6).
- Orji, J. I. (2005). *An assessment of impacts of poverty reduction programmes in Nigeria as a development strategy, 1970–2005* (Doctoral dissertation, St Clements University). <https://stclements.edu/grad/gradorji.pdf>
- Pye, L. W. (1966). *Aspects of political development*. Little, Brown.
- Roe, E. (1991). Development narratives, or making the best of blueprint development. *World Development*, 19(4), 287–300. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X\(91\)90177-J](https://doi.org/10.1016/0305-750X(91)90177-J)
- Voipio, T. (2000). The rise of the “governance” agenda: Good governance and aid policy in Finland. *Policy Studies*, 21(3), 249–266. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01442870050117098>
- Woolcock, M., & Narayan, D. (2000). Social capital: Implications for development theory, research, and policy. *World Bank Research Observer*, 15(2), 225–249.
- World Bank. (2003). *Community-driven development in Africa: Emerging lessons*. World Bank.
- World Bank. (2022). *Nigeria poverty assessment 2022: A better future for all Nigerians*. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/nigeria/publication/nigeria-poverty-assessment-2022>